

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

Second Living Lab Scrutinizing and Refining the Conceptual Model

VERSION 1.0

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies, located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to establish efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The objective of this document is to report the process conducted in the second living lab in Konya, Turkey on February 17th, 2022. The aim of the second living lab is to scrutinize and refine the conceptual model.

1. Introduction

This is the documentation of M4.2 of the “Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean” Grant Agreement Number 1923 project.

The document provides information on the preparations, participants, and activities of the milestone M4.2 “Second Living Lab scrutinizing and refining the conceptual model”.

The purpose of the second living lab (M4.2) held on February 17, 2022, in Konya city center was to build conceptual maps that would help us understand why and how the reference modes elicited in the first living lab (and verified by hard data) develop over time and what would be the response key performance indicators, if the proposed policies in the first living lab were adopted by the authorities and complied by the water users.

After having prepared and sent a bulletin to the participants of the first living lab, the research team organized the fourth round of field work prior to the second living lab, to foster trust and reinvoke stakeholders to the second living lab in person.

The M4.2 started with a brief reintroduction of individuals, recap of the first living lab, and reminder about the mechanistic of model building, reference modes, and key variables of interest. Following that, we started a discussion about what other variables are relevant for our model, and the nature of the relationships between variables. Unlike the first living lab, we did not form any breakout groups and maintained the discussion in the main plenary. The second living lab ended with the promise of the third living lab, in which the research team would come back with a complete simulation model, and a larger audience would be free to ask policy related questions to the model and discuss their results in the long term.

Overall, the outcomes of M4.2 will serve as a seed for the numerical model that will be developed by the research team, and the participants to the workshop will be revisited individually in a fifth round of field work, to work on and/or to validate the simulation model.

2. Second Living Lab for the Konya Closed Basin, Turkey Case Study

2.1. Process Towards the Workshop

This workshop was designed as a follow up to the achievements of the first workshop of the living lab in Konya on the 30th of September 2021 (please refer to M4.1). During almost the six months in between, so as not to lose contact with our key informants and stakeholders to the participatory governance analysis, firstly, we prepared a short bulletin of the first workshop, outlining its intended purpose, activity structure, intellectual outputs in the form of visual objects and the discussion on the road ahead. This bulletin in local language was sent to individual participants, indicating that we're wishing to meet them again in February 2022. Overall, the first living lab in September 2021 was designed in a sequence of "presentations" which outlined the methodological approach (system dynamics based participatory modeling) and "divergent activities" which opened the floor for dynamic problem identification and policy proposals, firstly developed within breakout groups and then represented and synthesized in plenary sessions. The first workshop helped us identify the problems of interest, as they develop over time regarding groundwater use and sustainability in an agricultural setting (the reference modes of our analysis) and prominent solutions (policy proposals) as spelled out by a diverse group of participants, involving farmers, professionals in agricultural management, groundwater specialists, conservationists, and academics.

During the way forward, the "reference modes" of the first workshop was verified with hard data and the policy proposal were clustered under several categories by our expert team. These were presented before the activities took start during the second workshop and they are presented in Section 2.1.3 in this document.

Shortly prior to the second workshop, our team consisting of facilitators, modelers and process coaches were in the field in Konya to reinforce the mutual trust that we are working to develop within the living lab and invite the participants once more, in person to the second workshop.

2.2. Invitees and Attendance to the Workshop

The list of invitees and the attendance to the second living lab are presented below in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. A diverse group of stakeholders, from academia to state institutions, NGOs, and farmers were involved in the discussions, as well as in the first living lab.

Table 1: List of invitees to the second workshop of the living lab

Affiliation	Title/Occupation
Alibeyhüyüğü Irrigation Cooperative	President
	Manager
Ankara University	Academic
Çumra Irrigation Union	President
	Manager
Chamber of Agriculture in Çumra	Agricultural Engineer
Nature Research Association	President
Nature Conservation Centre	Land and Water Programme Coordinator
DSİ	Geophysical Engineers
	Surface Waters Department Manager
	Monitoring and Appropriation Department Manager
	Land Consolidation Department Manager
	Groundwater Department Manager
Hydropolitics Association	Academic
Provincial Directorate of Agriculture	Agricultural Engineer
Konya Food and Agriculture University	Academic
Konya Commodity Exchange	Secretary General
Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP)	Project Development Coordinator and his team
Konya Leader Farmer Association	President
	Agricultural Engineers
	Farmers
Ova Irrigation Union	President
	Manager
Selçuk University	Academics
Turkish Foundation for Combating Soil Erosion (TEMA)	Officer
WWF Turkey	Officer
Konya Technical University	Academic

Table 2: Attendance to the second workshop of the living lab

Affiliation	Title/Occupation
Alibeyhüyüğü Irrigation Cooperative	Manager
	Assistant Manager
Ankara University	Academic
Çumra Irrigation Union	Manager
	Officer
Chamber of Agriculture in Çumra	Agricultural Engineer
DSİ	Geophysical Engineers (2)
	Surface Waters Department Manager
Hydropolitics Association	Academic
Konya Commodity Exchange	Officer
Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP)	Project Development Coordinator
	Engineer
Konya Leader Farmer Association	President
	Agricultural Engineer
	Farmers (4)
Turkish Foundation for Combating Soil Erosion (TEMA)	Officer
Total Attendance:	20

Figure 1 shows a photo with the research team and the attendees, at the end of the day.

Figure 1: Group photograph at the end of the workshop

2.3. Purpose of the Workshop

The workshop started with a couple of short presentation activities. Firstly, the research team and the living lab constituency was introduced once more, in person, considering the newcomers to the participatory modeling process. After that, the mechanistic of model building, starting with the reference modes, and following through key variables of interest, variable elicitation, causal mapping, and real time computer simulation was introduced with a non-technical language. This introduction was based on narratives of groundwater depletion to intuitively appeal to the workshop participants. A particular emphasis was given on the distinction on variables that accumulate over time (as for example the water in a water tank) and those which change instantaneously (as for example the water flowing in the tank in response to the valve that controls the inflow).

Thirdly, the reference modes elicited throughout the first workshop with corresponding time series data and the policy proposals clustered under four categories were introduced. Figures 2 - 10 show some of the reference modes elicited in the first workshop. These were presented to the second workshop plenary, along with related time series data.

Figure 2 shows the groundwater level. The graph on the left was drawn by participants of the first workshop; it represents their observations. The graph on the right-hand side is the average well-depth data for Çumra region, and it is coherent with the stakeholders' observations.

Figure 2: Groundwater level as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed average well depth time series data (on the right)

Figure 3 shows the plantation area of water-demanding crops. The graph on the left represents trefoil, corn, and other forage crops (bottom up). To compare stakeholder observations with hard data, we displayed the same three crop types in the graph on the right. The blue line represents trefoil plantation area, the red one represents corn plantation area, and the green line represents other forage crops plantation area. We see that although the relative sizes of plantation area for different crops are not captured well, the general trend observed by stakeholders is consistent with the data.

Figure 3: Land spared for water demanding crops as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed trefoil (blue), corn (red), and other forage crops (green) cultivated land data (on the right)

Figure 4 shows the wheat plantation area. The participants' observation in the first workshop shows a decreasing trend in wheat-grown land, and it is coherent with the hard data. The data presented in the graph on the right is for Çumra region.

B

Figure 4: Land spared for wheat as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed wheat-grown land data (on the right)

Figure 5 shows the total irrigated land. The graph on the left shows the past trend observed by participants of the first workshop (the black line), their future expectations (the blue line), and what they would like to see in the future – their desire (the green line). The vertical line in the middle of the graph presents the point in time, separating past and future. In parallel, the graph on the right shows hard data of irrigated land. It could be argued that the steady state of irrigated land the stakeholders expect and/or hope to see in the future has already been reached.

The black line in the graph shown in Figure 6 represents the change in the number of groundwater wells over time, as it had been observed by the participants of the first living lab. As it was the case in Figure 5, the vertical line in the middle of the graph represents the present time, separating the past from the future. The blue line shows the expected future behavior, while the green line shows the desired future behavior of the aforesaid variable.

Figure 5: Total irrigated land as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed total irrigated land data (on the right)

Figure 6: Number of groundwater wells over time drawn by the participants

In the first living lab, we faced some resistance from the participants because they were hesitant to talk openly about groundwater wells. The problem is that the correct number of wells in the basin is not known today. The locals estimate more than 100000 unlicensed wells. DSI (State Hydraulic Works) has not been issuing permits for groundwater wells since early 2000s, thus every well that has been dug since then is “illegal”. Also, no public authority has taken the inventory of wells in more than 10 years, so the subject of groundwater wells is the elephant in the room. However, a study on groundwater, the socio-economic analysis of groundwater use, and the causes of groundwater depletion must investigate the factors that

drive the change in groundwater wells. Therefore, even though hard data on number of wells is absent, we needed to build a reference behavior over time.

In Figure 7, the time series data of corn yield is presented. The seed variety and the harvest time determine whether the corn is silage or grain. The hard data obtained specifies this difference, and so does the farmers. In the previous rounds of field trip, we had heard about the increase in the corn yield, and we ended up having verified this observation with hard data as well.

Figure 7: Observed corn yield over time (source: TUIK, 2022)

Figure 8 shows the total plantation area of all cereals, including wheat, barley, oat etc. Contrary to first living lab participants' observations, the hard data does not indicate to a sharp decline in cereal plantation area.

Figure 8: Cereal plantation area as drawn by the participants (on the left) and observed total cereals plantation area data (on the right)

In Figure 9, we see the input costs in agriculture over time. The participants of the first living lab stated that the input costs had been increasing in time and they expected further increase in the costs; however, they wished that the costs would decrease in the future. The electricity cost has been increasing due to both increase in groundwater use and the consequent decrease in groundwater table. As groundwater table declines, the necessity for new wells increases, thus well digging costs are also incurred. On top of that, they mention the price increase in fertilizer and pesticides over the years.

Figure 9: Total input costs in agricultural production over time drawn by the participants

In the presentation, we also shared the elevation map of Konya Closed Basin (Figure 10 (a)), the average precipitation in Çumra region (Figure 10 (b)), and yearly average temperature data from 1975 to 2019 (Figure 10 (c)).

Figure 10: a) The elevation map of Konya Closed Basin b) The average precipitation from 1975 to 2020 in Çumra c) Yearly average temperature data over time in Çumra

Following these graphical representations of the reference modes, we briefly discussed the policy proposals in four categories, as discussed in the first workshop:

- Advanced public authority and cooperation among public institutions to regulate groundwater wells,
- Promoting higher technology irrigation systems, for information-based groundwater management,
- Enhancing surface water resources, through rain harvesting, use of wastewater, or inter basin water transfer projects,
- Subsidy schemes for local and water conserving crops instead of green plants, to control water demand.

After these presentations, the purpose of the day was announced as building of conceptual maps, that would help us understand “why and how these reference modes develop over time” and “what would be the response of key performance indicators, if the proposed policies were adopted by the authorities and complied by the water users”.

2.4. Workshop Activities

Table 3 shows the day plan of the second workshop, as presented to the participants. Prior to the second workshop, we had layered the problems that were put forward by the participants in the first workshop, to focus on specific and prominent issues one by one instead of all at once. To that end, we prepared Table 4, and communicated our focus issues in each session to the participants and discussed their relevance/convenience. In the morning, our goal was to work on the relationship between groundwater supply and demand, considering groundwater wells and agricultural product yields. In the afternoon, we aimed to study the crop choice, excluding yield this time. For both morning and afternoon sessions, we planned a similar process (Table 3), in which we would first come to an agreement with the participants on problem definition and initial model template. Then, we would study the matter at hand deeply to enhance the diagram, add new variables as appropriate and elicit the relationships among those.

Table 3: Day Plan

Morning	09:00 AM	Greeting
	09:30 AM	Opening: Meet & greet Recap of the 1st workshop
	10:00 AM	1st Session: Agreement on problem definition & model diagram
	10:30 AM	Coffee Break
	10:50 AM	2nd Session: Conceptual Modelling Model-based discussion on policy proposals
Afternoon	1:00 PM	Sample Model Simulation
	1:30 PM	3rd Session: Agreement on problem definition & model diagram
	2:00 PM	Coffee Break
	2:20 PM	4th Session: Conceptual Modelling Model-based discussion on policy proposals
	3:30 PM	Closing

Table 4: Planned Modeling Activities

	Planned Modeling Activities			
		I (Morning)	II (Afternoon)	III (To be completed by the research team)
Issues Put Forth During the First Workshop	Groundwater Level	X	X	X
	Number of Wells	X	X	X
	Yield	X		
	Green Plant vs Cereals Area		X	
	Traditional vs Modern Irrigation			X

Opening Session

Following the greeting and recap of the first living lab, the opening session focused on building simple causal loop diagrams. The facilitator directed the participants into conceiving variables as stocks and flows. For convenience we started with groundwater as a stock variable, and recharge and extraction as flow variables. By asking questions that can be considered mind exercises, for instance, “What happens if extraction is higher than recharge?” or “What happens to the groundwater stock if recharge is equal to extraction?”, the facilitator familiarized participants with the relationships between stocks and flows. While the facilitator led the discussion and translated what is being said to the whiteboard, modelers simultaneously transferred the white board into Stella Architect, the software being used for modeling and reflected it in the big projection screen. Figure 11 shows the initial causal loop diagram that was elicited in this part, as shown on the projection screen during the workshop.

Figure 11: The causal loop diagram elicited in the first session, as shown on the projection screen

After that, as in the previous workshop, a small, simplistic simulation model was built on Stella Architect, to introduce the software to the newcomers and to remind second timers. Figure 12 shows the model, including only one (groundwater level) stock and two flow variables (consumption and recharge), and the numeric output it produces (the graph on the right, where we observe a decrease in groundwater level over time. We also briefly experimented with this model, to see how the groundwater level changes if we change the recharge, green plant area, or water consumption need per unit area.

Figure 12: The simple model simulated in the first workshop

1st Session

At the beginning of this session, a visual representation of the first model layer to be studied (with groundwater level, wells, and agricultural product yield – single crop variety assumption) was presented to the participants (Figure 13).

Figure 13: The visual representation of the I (morning) column in Table 4

As shown in Figure 14, groundwater level and number of active wells were represented as stock variables, and the facilitator started a discussion on the appropriate flow variables. After agreeing on the physical model and the initial stock-flow template, there was a short break and the workshop resumed with the 2nd session.

Figure 14: Stock-flow representation of groundwater level and number of active wells

2nd Session

The second session started with exploring questions related to the causes of flows on the sock-flow diagram, such as “what causes increase in groundwater levels?”, or “what causes decrease in the number of active wells?”. However, there were disagreements and misunderstandings among the group, which slowed down the process and diverted the discussion towards clarification of some particular issues: Although all participants consented to the well digging inflow to number of active wells stock, there were disagreements regarding the outflow (drying of wells). To build consensus, the facilitator directed the conversation towards maximum possible groundwater supply (capacity of groundwater supply) in case of presumptive infinite groundwater demand, given the groundwater level and number of active wells. However, the participants were rather unconvinced about the infinite groundwater demand assumption. The discussion on groundwater supply capacity led us to a conversation about well pumps, their power, and flow rates of wells. Contrary to the research team’s prior judgement, the participants argued that higher number wells in a unit area would not affect the flow rate capacity of an individual active well. The session carried on with discussions regarding the meanings of different concepts. For example, the maximum amount of groundwater a single well can produce in one season was initially referred to as “well flow rate”, however, after having understood that the participants conceive well flow rate in terms of volume of water obtained per second, we changed the name of this variable to “well capacity”. The session ended with the promise on working “demand side” of the problem, which was expected to clarify us on the drivers of changing groundwater demand and the group joined the lunch break.

3rd Session

After lunch, since the morning session was more controversial and demanding that was anticipated by the research team, we had to cancel the presentation on morning’s simulation experiments for which the model was yet uncomplete and focused on groundwater demand to avoid further complication over the supply discussion and complete the envisioned interactions between supply and demand. Thus, we started talking about the yield, assuming the farmers only cultivate corn – a green, high water demanding crop. Participants agreed that

more irrigation increases corn yield, up to a certain point. This relationship is drawn in a graph (Figure 15).

Figure 15: The relationship between irrigation and corn yield. The y-axis represents yield, and the x-axis represents irrigation level.

Participants came up with other factors affecting corn yield, such as fertilizer use, pest control, precipitation, and seed variety. Following that, we discussed the relative importance of these factors on crop yield.

Then, the facilitator asked the following question: What happens if we do not obtain the yield we aimed, i.e if there is a “yield gap” perceived by the farmer? Some participants agreed that they would try different levels of inputs in the next crop season to achieve the yield target. However, barriers were observed while trying the further the discussion and variable elicitation towards the impact of higher water demand on well exploitation and well construction, which was expected to close the feedback causality between groundwater water supply and demand. First barrier was farmers being defensive on water overuse and well construction, because this attitude was known as politically incorrect. Second barrier was some participants from public institutions being shy on openly speaking about uncontrolled water use and well constructions although these were matters under their authority. Thirdly, some public officials were discontent with the concept of “target yield” arguing that was showing the farmers as “greedy” although indeed it was a national policy to produce the green crops (here corn) in sufficient yield.

Because of defensive attitudes towards the concept of “target yield” and the impact of “yield gap” on increase in water demand, we found it more convenient to switch towards the second model template earlier than it was originally planned which aimed discussion the transformation between high and low water demanding crops. In the meanwhile, some other participants were already arguing that if a farmer fails to obtain enough yield in a season, they might switch to another crop in the next, which brought us to the crop choice discussion. Figure 16 shows the visual representation of the second (afternoon) column in Table 4, which assumes two crops – corn and wheat.

Figure 16: The visual representation of the II (afternoon) column in Table 4

We added *green plant area* and *cereal area* variables to our conceptual model and given the argument that a farmer might switch from one crop to another in case they do not achieve their yield goal, we connected those two variables. All agreed that the crop choice inevitably affects the water consumption need per unit area, and consequently altering the groundwater demand. Participants mentioned that rainwater harvesting, and surface water use also alter groundwater demand, thus, these variables were also added to the conceptual model. Lastly, the facilitator pointed to the relationship between demand and supply and connected *water consumption need* variable to *consumption* outflow.

Figure 17 shows the progress made in this session, as drawn on the white board by the facilitator.

Figure 17: The progress in the conceptual model in the third session

4th Session

At the last session of the day, we started a discussion on the policy proposal regarding the crop choice. Some participants argued that switching to cereals from green plants may not be useful in terms of conserving water, because winter crops are also being irrigated. Additionally, they mentioned the big picture impacts of abandoning corn and other green plants in the basin, as a considerable portion of the national demand for these products are supplied by the region. So, we concluded that instead of abandoning certain crops, crop rotation schemes would be a better policy proposal for the national interest and in terms of groundwater demand combined. Thus, we changed the *cereal area* variable to *crop rotation area* and the *adopting cereal* variable to *adopting crop rotation*.

Following that, we discussed the increase in irrigated land and the drivers of that change. In that discussion, the change in the precipitation regime (droughts), the low quality of pasture areas, and decrease in surface water availability are pointed out by participants as drivers of increase in dependency on groundwater, thus the increase in number of groundwater wells.

Observing that the intellectual effort demanded from the participants to focus on the priorly agreed problems of the modeling activity had become overwhelming; we decided to commence the workshop without completing the announced day plan.

Throughout the workshop, the facilitator transcribed the progress made on the whiteboard in parallel to the plenary discussions, and the modelers translated the content on the whiteboard to Stella Architect. The complete conceptual map created in Stella Architect during the second workshop is shown in Figure 18.

2.5. Fundamental Outcomes

Prior to the second living lab, we started building a seed model based on what we have learnt in the previous field trips and the first living lab. Combined with the learnings from the second living lab, below is the structure of that seed model (Figure 19). This model is in line with the assumptions of the first scenario that we presented in Table 4, column I (morning); we consider the groundwater, product yield, and the number of active wells, under the assumption of a single crop variety.

Figure 19: The seed model

In this seed model, there are two main stocks, namely, *Groundwater* and *Number of Active Wells*. The *Groundwater* stock is fed by the *recharge* inflow and declines with *water consumption* outflow. The *Number of Active Wells* stock increases by *well digging* and declines with *drying of wells*.

The main feedback loops of this model are presented in Figures 20 – 23.

The groundwater demand is driven by the *yield goal*. The yield goal is determined by the revenue (or more precisely, profit) goal, however in this seed model it is taken as an external variable. In case the *obtained yield* in a season is below the goal, there appears a *yield gap*, which can be fulfilled by more irrigation, fertilizer, or pest control in the following season, (See Section 2.1.4). In this model, we disregard the other agricultural inputs and include only irrigation because we focus on the water consumption. Thus, as in Figure 20, the *yield gap* drives the change in *water consumption goal*, which in fact is a measure of the additional water a farmer wishes to use for irrigation. The *desired water consumption* is presented as a stock variable for structural consistency (the change in the yield gap impacts the desired water consumption of the following season). The *water consumption goal* impacts the *water consumption gap* directly and indirectly through actual *water consumption*, creating two feedback loops, one reinforcing and one balancing, as seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Reinforcing R1 and balancing B1 loops between yield and water consumption variables

The *groundwater table* changes in parallel to the *Groundwater stock*, which represents the volume. *Groundwater table* impacts the *drying of wells* (for instance, if the groundwater table falls to a level below the well depth, the well dries), as in Figure 21. If more wells dry, the *Number of Active Wells* declines, and so does the *maximum possible gw supply*. Therefore, *potential water consumption* and thus the *water consumption* could be less than what they could otherwise be. In the general sense, what this loop tells us is that in case of infrastructure loss due to drying of wells, we could not extract as much water, thus the decrease in *Groundwater* would be less than what it otherwise would be.

Figure 21: The balancing B2 loop, drying of wells

The balancing loop B3 in Figure 22 captures the dynamics of the circular relationship between *Groundwater* stock and the *average well capacity*. As *groundwater table* decreases, the *average well capacity* also decreases. It should be mentioned here that the *average well capacity* is defined as the maximum volume of water that can be extracted from an average well, with constant pump power. We obtain *maximum possible groundwater supply* from *average well capacity* and *number of active wells*. This variable represents the potential maximum supply of groundwater, with the existing infrastructure. Therefore, when *average well capacity* decreases, so does the *maximum possible gw supply* and the *potential water consumption*. As a result, even when the *water consumption goal* is high, we cannot extract more than the maximum possible supply, so the decrease *Groundwater* stock would be less than what it otherwise would be.

Figure 22: The balancing B3 loop, capturing the dynamics of well capacity

Figure 23 shows a very simple and straightforward loop. If the *Number of Active Wells* decrease, the *well deficit* increases. As a result, farmers would be inclined to dig more wells, increasing the *Number of Active Wells*.

Figure 23: The balancing B4 loop, well digging

3. The Road Ahead

In the following six months, the research team will be developing the simulation model, based on the conceptual model that we started to build in the second living lab. In that period, we will be in touch with the stakeholders for two main reasons: First, we will need to further develop the model with them and validate the model structure with their knowledge of the field. Second, we want them to develop a feeling of ownership on the model, so that they remain interested and involved in the modeling process and further develop our mutual trust-based relationship with them. However, during the progress of the model, we do not plan to arrange a collective plenary session; instead, we plan to have online sessions, phone calls, or visits to each stakeholder separately.

At the end of the model building and validation process, we will organize the third and final living lab, and invite a larger number of stakeholders this time to present the model and its outputs. The goal will be to have an interactive scenario analysis and participatory policy design session with a larger stakeholder group. In the third living lab, the participants will be able to ask their policy related questions to the model itself, and the model will reveal the long-term outcomes of proposed policy scenarios.